

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Interview Date: _____

Company Name: _____

Interviewee Name: _____

Introduction to the Interview (5 minutes)

1. Interview Schedule
 - There will be 1 hour interview.
2. Presentation of Research Purpose
 - Slides
3. Ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of the information
 - It is to inform you that all information will be treated confidentially, and your identity will remain anonymous in any published materials.
 - All the data will be stored in password-protected documents and only the research team will have access to it.
 - We will remove any personally identifiable information (names, company names, project details) from the data. We will use general references like "Participant 1" and "Company A" in our reports.
4. Consent for participation and recording
 - Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you can choose to skip questions or withdraw from the interview at any point without any consequences.
 - Do you agree to participate in this interview based on the information provided?
 - Would it be okay if I record this interview and take notes for accuracy? The recording will only be used for research purposes, and it will be kept confidential.

Background Questions (5 - 10 minutes)

1. Can you describe your role within the company and your key responsibilities?
2. How long have you been in your current role and what is your prior experience?
3. What are the primary teams typically involved in your projects, how large are they, and are there any additional key stakeholders?

Topics/Themes to be covered in the interview:

1. **Architectural change overview? (10 – 15 minutes)**
 - a. Can you please give a brief overview of your software and system architecture practices?
 - b. What are the common types of architectural changes that occur in your project?
 - c. How often do they occur?
 - d. What are the common sources of those changes? Where do they originate?
2. **Methods / Tools to document architecture changes? (15 - 20 minutes)**
 - a. How important do you consider documenting architectural changes?

- i. Do you use any specific tools or methods to document architectural changes in your systems?
 - ii. At what level of abstraction/formalism do you model the architecture?
 - iii. How do these tools / methods integrate into your workflow?
 - iv. How do these tools or methods or ways of modelling change over time throughout the different phases of projects?
 - b. How do you manage to keep the documentation up to date?
 - c. Are you concerned about keeping consistency among the different architectural documents?
 - i. If yes, how do you ensure it?
 - d. In your current projects, does your team consider maintaining version control for architectural documentation? If yes, how do you incorporate version control in your project?
 - e. What features or elements do you believe are missing from the current documentation practices that could enhance their effectiveness?
 - f. Hypothetically, if you could implement any new tools or technologies to aid in documentation, what would they be and why?
 - g. What aspects of documentation do you want to improve and why?

3. Communication between teams? (15 - 20 minutes)

- a. Who do you think is important to communicate architectural changes to and what communication mechanism do you use to communicate these changes?
- b. While working with different teams, do you think it is important to maintain cohesiveness and clarity in architectural documentation? If yes, how do you ensure it?
- c. If you had the opportunity to implement three changes to improve the way your company handles communicating software architecture changes across different teams, what would they be?
- d. What improvements would you like to see in your current process to prevent or overcome the challenges you face during the collaboration and communication of architectural changes?

Quick checkout

- Stop recording
- Thank you for joining the interview
- We will get back to you with our insights